

Appendix A

Video simulation

File: soc_simulation.mp4

The video simulation depicts interactions between students during the execution of a single assignment. Navy blue nodes represent students, green nodes represent teachers, and gray edges indicate the fork operation from teachers to students. Navy blue edges represent a review request, while green edges represent a review submission. In the simulation, we observe interactions between a class of 5 students and another with 6 students. Although this example differs from the one explained in the main text, the logic of operation remains the same.

Note: The video is also available online: <https://youtu.be/BJ7KLoLABl8>